

ANALYSIS OF TRANSLATION STRATEGIES FOR SLANG WORDS IN THE WEBTOON LARA(S)HATI

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Abstract

Slang presents challenges for translators because it often depends on context and is rooted in its original culture. This study aims to analyze the forms of slang and translation strategies used in the Webtoon Lara(s)hati. This study uses a qualitative descriptive method to identify and analyze the slang and translation strategies applied. The data were analyzed using the theories of Yule (2010) and Bloomfield (1933) on slang and Baker (1992) on translation strategies. The results of the analysis show that there are 58 forms of slang, consisting of 15 borrowings (26%), 12 interjections (21%), 8 funny mispronunciations (14%), 7 coinages (12%), 6 acronyms and borrowings (10%), and 4 derivations (7%). There are 6 translation strategies used, consisting of paraphrase using a related word (16 or 28%), paraphrase using an unrelated word (14 or 24%), cultural substitution (13 or 22%), omission (7 or 12%), using more neutral/less expressive words (5 or 9%), and using a more general words (3 or 5%). Based on these findings, the borrowing form is the most dominant, indicating the speakers' efforts to build familiarity with their group. Paraphrasing using a related word is the most frequently applied, indicating the translator's efforts to preserve the meaning and nuances in the source language.

INTRODUCTION

Language is constantly evolving and changing within society. These shifts are triggered by its relationship with the culture and socio - economics of its speakers (Hasriani, 2023). This dynamic nature has

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***Related declarations are provided in the final section of this article.*

Led to the emergence of a variety of colloquial terms used by different groups of people in different contexts. Triadi & Pradanti (2025) explain that a variety of colloquial terms refers to a variation of language that is formed in a speech community with an informal form. The existence of this linguistic diversity indirectly encourages creativity or innovation among speakers in inventing or modifying language. This gives rise to new terms that are integrated into everyday conversation. For example, among Generation Z, words tend to undergo changes, from what was originally considered rude or sarcastic to becoming a symbol of familiarity (Triadi & Pradianti, 2025). For example, the word “cuk” is usually used to address someone close. The original form of that word is “jancuk”, which is a curse word. This change in word can be called a slang. Morgan (2025) explains that a slang is an informal vocabulary that spread and developed within communities. It is created from humor, rebellion, or the need to build a sense of belonging.

Slangs grow very quickly in everyday conversation. Moreover, it also spread to benefit writers in adding color to their work. In this globalization era, it is easy to read any writings in a digital form. One of those is Webtoon. It is a popular digital comic platform from South Korea that now provides works from various countries. Webtoon also has a variety of genres. One of the most popular genres is teen fiction. The use of slang makes it has an expressive language style. Slang plays an important role in a language because it helps to add color, humor, and nuances (Marco, 2025). One of the Indonesian teen fiction works on Webtoon is *Lara(s)hati*. This work has successfully gathered 49.9 million readers on the platform. Webtoon *Lara(s)hati* is one of the Indonesian works available in English. The role of translators makes it possible to reach international readers.

However, translating slang often makes translators face some challenges. The meaning of slang is often depends on the context. Furthermore, the group of speakers and situation also makes it has varying meanings. On top of that, slang usually contains cultural terms, as well as words and phrases that are very attached to their original culture (Marco, 2025). The process of translating slang is not simple. It cannot be translated directly because the result would not fully express the meaning and also could lead to a nonsensical and offensive translation (Morgan, 2025). It is very important for the translators to have a deep understanding of the cultural context of the slang, along with its connotations or implied meanings (Marco, 2025).

Therefore, this study aims to analyze how translators overcome the challenges of translating slang. This study focuses on two things, namely analyzing the forms of slang found in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati* and the strategies used by translators in transferring the meaning from Indonesian to English. The author uses Yule's (2010) theory to classify the types of slang encountered. Yule (2010) divides slang into ten types, namely acronym, borrowing, blending,

coinage, conversion, compounding, clipping, derivation, back formation, and multiple processes. In addition, the author also uses Bloomfield's (1933) theory on interjections and funny mispronunciations because the author found some slang data related to this theory. Thus, Bloomfield's (1933) theory is used to fill the limitations of Yule's (2010) theory, considering that there are some slang words that are not covered in that theory. Furthermore, in analyzing the strategies used, the author uses Baker's (1992) theory, which divides translation strategies into eight categories, namely translation by a more general word, translation by a more neutral/less expressive word, translation by cultural substitution, translation using a loan word plus explanations, translation by paraphrase using a related word, translation by paraphrase using an unrelated word, translation by omission, and translation by illustration.

Research on slang and translation strategies has been conducted previously. This research serves as a reference for developing a strong interpretation of the slang phenomenon on which this study focuses. For example, Istiqomah et al (2020) analyzed the translation strategies used in the Webtoon *My Pre-Wedding*. The results showed that translators mostly used the omission strategy, which indicates that its use did not interfere with the storyline and the meaning was still conveyed well. Furthermore, Megalasari & Putri (2024) researched the strategies and accuracy of fan translations related to slang in the Webtoon *Pasutri Gaje*. The results of the study explain that fan translations are quite accurate, although there are still challenges with cultural terms. Then, Rahmah et al (2024) investigated slang translation strategies in the subtitles of the movie *Inside Out 2*. The findings show that direct translation strategies are most often used by translators because they are believed to be more efficient and maintain accurate meaning. There is also Wardhani (2023), who examined the analysis of slang in the novel *Dikta dan Hukum*. The results of the analysis explain that abbreviated slang is most commonly found. This shows creativity and efficiency in everyday conversation. In addition, Tasyarasita et al (2023) investigated the variety of slang used by Gen Z teenagers on the social media platform TikTok. Their findings explain that funny mispronunciations are the most common form of slang. This indicates that Gen Z often uses creativity and humor in their conversations.

METHOD

In this research, a qualitative descriptive method is used to identify and analyze slang and translation strategies used. The data sources in this study are episodes in Indonesian as the source language (SL) and episodes in English as the target language (TL) in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati*,

focusing on dialogues containing slang. Data is collected using document analysis techniques by examining dialogues containing slang and classifying their types, as well as analyzing the strategies used to translate the grouped data. The findings are then described and conclusions are drawn based on the analysis presented.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Slang Forms Found in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati*

Based on the data collected and analyzed, 58 slang forms were found in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati*. From the 58 data points, there are 5 of the 10 slang forms mentioned by Yule (2010), namely coinage, acronym, clipping, derivation, and borrowing. The findings also included 2 forms of slang proposed by Bloomfield (1933), namely interjections and funny mispronunciations. The slang findings are distributed in the following table:

Table 1. Findings of Slang Forms in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati*

No.	Slang Form	Frequency	Percentage
1	Coinage	7	12%
2	Acronym	6	10%
3	Clipping	6	10%
4	Borrowing	15	26%
5	Derivation	4	7%
6	Interjections	12	21%
7	Funny mispronunciations	8	14%
Total		58	100%

The data presented in the table shows that the most common form of slang is borrowing, with 15 instances (26%), followed by interjections with 12 instances (21%), funny mispronunciations with 8 instances (14%), coinage with 7 instances (12%), acronyms and borrowing with 6 instances (10%), and the least common form of slang is derivation, with 4 instances (7%). The findings on slang can be illustrated in the following examples.

1. Coinage

Coinage refers to a slang that is formed by creating a completely new term (Wardhani, 2023).

Example:

Data 1

“Norak banget dah lo!”

The sentence was said by Radi when Kartika kept trying to get involved in Nathan’s girlfriend business. The word “Norak” in this sentence is a form of coinage slang because it is a new term that has no etymology. The *KBBI* defines it as “very excessive.”

Data 2

“Gue punya yang lebih kece nih”

Tio wanted to ruin Radi’s reputation by arranging a good sneaky plan. The word “kece” in this sentence is a new word, which in the *KBBI* means “beautiful”. However, its meaning has developed in everyday use. It could also refer to something attractive or has a good style.

2. Acronym

An acronym is a type of slang that is formed by combining the initial letters or syllables of several words (Wardhani, 2023).

Example:

Data 1

“HAHAHA gercep abiss!!”

This sentence is Jordan's response to Rendi, who preceded Tio's plan to approach Laras. In this case, the word “gercep” is an abbreviation of “gerak cepat” (move fast), which describes someone who is very attentive.

Data 2

“Ayo Rad ikutan! Cemen lo ah!”

This sentence is Radi's friend teasing him because he is tired and unable to play soccer. The word “cemen” in this sentence is an abbreviation of “cetek mental” which means not having any courage.

3. Clipping

Clipping is the process of shortening words by removing some syllables (Wardhani, 2023).

Example:

Data 1

“No pic hoax, gan.”

Jordan said this to Maya to ask for proof of his brother's relationship with Laras. The word “gan” in this sentence is a shortened form of the word “juragan,” which is a familiar greeting or nickname for someone close .

Data 2

“Sepi nih! Sebat dulu apa ya?”

This sentence was said by Radi when he went ahead of his friends to class after PE. In this sentence, the word “sebat” is a shortened form of the word “sebatang.” It refers to the activity of smoking a cigarette.

4. Borrowing

Borrowing is a form of slang that is taken from other languages (Wardhani, 2023). Example:

Data 1

“Biar mingkem anak-anak PEDAL!”

This sentence was said by Radi to state his intention to destroy the PEDAL group. The word “mingkem” is a Javanese word, which in *Kamus Bahasa Jawa* means “to shut up”.

Data 2

“Ah kampret! Gue gaplok lo!”

Radi said this sentence because he felt annoyed when Nathan teased him for having no girlfriend. The word “gaplok” in this sentence is a Sundanese word, which in the *KBBI* means “to hit with the palm of the hand.”

5. Derivation

Derivation is the formation of slang by adding affixes and suffixes to existing words, which also changes their part of speech (Wardhani, 2023).

Example:

Data 1

“Udah ya, kalian ga usah ngomporin dulu.”

Jordan said this sentence when he tried to stop his friends from heating up the situation between Sugeng and Radi. In this sentence, the word “ngomporin” has the root word “kompor,” which is a noun. The addition of the suffix “-in” and the prefix “meng-”, which is adjusted to “ng-”, changes it into a verb, which in this context means to provoke or incite.

Data 2

“Yaudah, istirahat dulu deh, sori gue ngegas.”

Radi said this sentence because he felt sorry. Maya was upset because Radi’s could not teach her to confess to Nathan in a calm way. The word “ngegas” in this sentence comes from the noun “gas”. The sentence then changes into a verb because of the addition of the prefix “nge”. When a person uses the word “Ngegas”, it means that they speak in a high and rude tone.

6. Interjections

Interjections refer to slang forms used to express an emotion or feeling, which do not have affixes or syntactic support in other forms (Tasyarasita et al., 2023).

Example:

Data 1

“Gilaaa! ‘Gue anak PEDAL’ katanya.”

The reaction was from one of the students in the canteen when he saw his friend got teased. There was someone who glued a piece of paper with a mocking sentence on his back. The word “gila” in this context is a spontaneous response or reaction of surprise.

Data 2

“Cieeee, Anak PEDAL hahaha!”

This taunt was shouted by other students when they saw the note stuck to their friend’s back. In this sentence, the word “cie” is an exclamation used to tease someone who has a romantic feeling or crush on other people.

7. Funny mispronunciations

Funny mispronunciations refer to a form of deliberate change in the pronunciation of a word (Tasyarasita et al., 2023).

Example:

Data 1

“Dia lebih woles daripada si Sugeng.”

Radi said this when he was about to ask Marco about PEDAL. The word “woles” is a reversal of the word “selow,” which comes from the English word “slow.” In this context, “woles” refers to someone who has a relaxed personality.

Data 2

“Wah sabi lah.”

This sentence is Yopi’s response to Jordan, who asked to have a meeting after learning about the argument between Radi and Sugeng. The word “sabi” is a reversal of the word “bisa”, which in this case is a word used to express agreement or capability.

Translation strategies for slang used in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati*

The researcher found 6 strategies out of the 8 strategies proposed by Baker (1992), namely translation by a more general word, translation by a more neutral/less expressive word, translation by cultural substitution, translation by paraphrase using related words, translation by paraphrase using unrelated words, and translation by omission. The results of the strategy analysis are detailed in the following table:

Table 2. Translation Strategies Used in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati*

No.	Translation Strategies	Frequency	Percentage
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1	Translation by a more general word	3	5%
2	Translation by a more neutral/less expressive word	5	9%
3	Translation by cultural substitution	13	22%
4	Translation by paraphrase using a related word	16	28%
5	Translation by paraphrase using an unrelated word	14	24%
6	Translation by omission	7	12%
Total		58	100%

The data distributed in the table shows that the translation strategy by paraphrase using a related word is most frequently used in translating slang, which is a total of 16 (28%), followed by the translation strategy by paraphrase using an unrelated word, with a total of 14 (24%), translation by cultural substitution with a total of 13 (22%), translation by omission with a total of 7 (12%), translation by a more neutral/less expressive word with a total of 5 (9%), and the least frequently used strategy is translation by a more general word, with a total of 3 (5%). The translation strategies found can be explained through the following examples.

1. Translation by a more general word

This strategy is used to translate a specific word in the source language with a more general term in the target language (Rahmah et al., 2024).

Example:

Data 1

SL: “Sepi nih! Sebat dulu apa ya?” TL: “No one’s here! Should I smoke?”

The word “sebat” refers specifically to the activity of smoking a cigarette while relaxing for a moment. Since there is no equivalent word to describe this meaning, the translator uses a more general term, “smoke,” which in the Merriam-Webster dictionary means “to emit or exhale smoke.”

Data 2

SL: “Gue mau minta tolong nih, hehehe.” TL: “I need a favor, hehehe.”

The word “gue” is an informal form of the word “saya”. In the source language, this pronoun is used to express a level of familiarity with someone. However, English does not have such distinctions. Therefore, the word ‘gue’ is translated as “I”, which is a pronoun used in all contexts, both formal and Informal.

2. Translation by a more neutral/less expressive word

This strategy is used to translate terms that have strong emotional connotations and are not easily transferred into the target language by using a more neutral/less expressive word or phrases (Megalasari & Putri, 2024).

Example:

Data 1

SL: “Lo sengotot itu ya, Rad? TL: “Why’re you so persistent?”

The word “ngotot” in slang means to insist, or to be stubborn. In this case, the word is translated as “persistent,” which in the Cambridge Dictionary means “someone who continues doing something or tries to do something in a determined way.” In this case, the word “persistent” has a more subtle impression, as it only describes a person who is purposeful, without carrying the “stubborn” context.

Data 2

SL: “Gue mewek depan ini cewek.”

TL: “I ended up crying in front of this girl.”

The word “mewek” in slang means crying softly, in a tone similar to whining. In the *KBBI*, the word “mewek” refers to someone who starts crying, as seen from a disappointed face and pursed lips. The word is translated as “crying,” which has a less expressive meaning, as it only describes someone who sheds tears due to an emotion.

3. Translation by cultural substitution

This translation strategy is used in cases where there is a cultural element in the source language that is relevant or has the same meaning in the target culture (Volf, as cited in Rahmah et al., 2024)

Example:

Data 1

SL: “Cuy! Pinjem pulpen ya!”

TL: “Dude, Let me borrow your pen!”

The word “cuy” in slang is often used as a friendly address to close friends. This word has an equivalent in the target language culture, namely “dude”. Both words are used as a casual greeting or familiar nickname among friends.

Data 2

SL: “Anjir! Kok jadi gue pikirin?!”

TL: “Geez! Why am I dwelling on it now?”

The word “anjir” is used to express spontaneous reactions such as surprise, admiration, or anger. In this case, the word is substituted with “Geez,” which in the target language comes from the word “Jesus,” equivalent to “Oh my God” or “Oh dear.”

4. Translation by paraphrase using a related word

This strategy is applied by translating a word in the target language with a word or phrase that has a meaning that is similar or closely associated (Megalasari & Putri, 2024).

Example:

Data 1

SL: “Biar mingkem anak-anak PEDAL!”

TL: “I’ll shut up those PEDAL boys for good!”

The word “mingkem” is a Javanese word. According to *Kamus Bahasa Jawa*, this word means to shut someone’s mouth. The word is translated as “shut up,” which means to be quite. This translation has a meaning that is still related to the term in the source language, as it still describes the act of silencing someone. Data 2

SL: “Biar gue yang bacot di sana.” TL: “I’ll spout out some bullshit.”

The word “bacot” is an abbreviation of the phrase “banyak cocot”. It translates to “spout out some bullshit”, which means to utter some boasting. This translation has a meaning related to the source language term. They both convey the meaning of someone who talks a lot of nonsense.

5. Translation by paraphrase using an unrelated word

This strategy is used by translating a word into the target language with a word or phrase that has no semantic connection to the source language (Megalasari & Putri, 2024).

Example:

Data 1

SL: “Ogah! Gue ada les bahasa Inggris tau!” TL: “Spare me! I have English tutoring!”

The word “ogah” in this sentence is a term that indicates reluctance or unwillingness. Since there is no equivalent in the target language, the translator renders the word as “spare me,” which also means “don’t bother me.” Although the translation has no contextual connection to the source language, the nuance is preserved.

Data 2

SL: “Lo sewot banget” TL: “What’s with you?”

The word “sewot” refers to feelings of annoyance or irritation that cause a person to grumble and talk a lot. In this case, the meaning is translated as “what's with you?” which in Indonesian means “Ada apa denganmu?”. The translation still conveys the nuance of the source language well, even though it does not fully capture the meaning.

6. Translation by omission

This strategy is used to eliminate a word in the source language that is considered unimportant for describing the context or does not have an exact equivalent in the target language (Juining & Kusuma, as cited in Rahmah et al., 2024) Example:

Data 1

SL: “Berisik woi! Bajingan!” TL: “Shut up already!”

The word “bajingan” is an interjection or curse word that expresses annoyance or anger.

However, this nuance is lost in the target language and is instead translated as “shut up already!” This translation focuses on conveying the core meaning and sacrifices the expressive elements of the source language.

Data 2

SL: “Udah ya, kalian ga usah ngomporin.”

TL: “Stop it, you guys!”

The word “ngomporin” in slang means to provoke or stir up a situation. This word is omitted in the translation process and simplified to “you guys!”. This translation simplifies the dialogue by removing the terms in the source language culture to maintain naturalness.

CONCLUSION

This study analyzes the slang forms found in the Webtoon *Lara(s)hati* and the strategies used by translators to overcome the challenges in translating such slang. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that there are seven forms of slang found, with borrowing being the most frequently used. It suggests that speakers try to create a sense of belonging with the members of their group. Furthermore, there are 6 translation strategies used, with paraphrase using a related word being the most dominant, followed by paraphrase using an unrelated word. This present study is in line with the previous researches conducted by Cayana (2024) and Rahmi (2025). This indicates that in dealing with a word that has no equivalent in the target language, translators interpret the context while trying to preserve the meaning and nuance in the source language.

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References

Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa. (n.d.). *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI) daring*. <https://kbbi.web.id/>

Baker, M. (1992). *In other words: A coursebook on translation*. Routledge.

Balai Bahasa Jawa Tengah. (2017). Mingkem. In *Kamus Bahasa Jawa – Indonesia* (2nd ed., p. 166).

Bloomfield, L. (1933). *Language*. Henry Holt and Company.

Cambridge Dictionary. (n.d.). Persistent. In *Cambridge.org dictionary*. Retrieved October 2025, from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/persistent>

Cayana, V. T. (2024). An analysis of slang expressions used in Brooklyn Nine-Nine American TV series. *ELSA*, 5(1), 28–40. <https://doi.org/10.63848/elsa.v05n1.4>

Hasriani. (2023). *Ragam bahasa slang dalam komunikasi digital*. Indonesia Emas Group.

Istiqomah, L., Khasanah, D., Tauhida, A., Ningtyas, R. A., & Rohimah, A. N. (2020). Indonesian to English translation strategies used in Webtoon “My Pre-Wedding”. *Elsya: Journal of English Language Studies*, 2(2), 37–42. <https://doi.org/10.31849/elsya.v2i2.4024>

Marco, P. D. (2025a). *Argot lexicon*. Pasquale De Marco.

Marco, P. D. (2025b). *Literary translation skills unlocked*. Pasquale De Marco.

Megalasari, R. I., & Putri, A. A. (2024). Indonesian slang: Translation strategies and accuracy assessment in the Pasutri Gaje Webtoon’s English fan translations. *Journal of Language, Literature, and Teaching*, 6(2), 14–30. <https://doi.org/10.35529/jllte.v6i2.14-30>

Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Smoke. In *Merriam-Webster.com dictionary*. Retrieved October 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/smoke>

Morgan, G. (2025). *Awkward translation*. Publifye AS.

Rahmah, A. A., Wildan, G. G., & Fitriyah, F. (2025). Translation strategies for slang words in the subtitles of film “Inside Out 2.” *Pujangga*, 10(2), 180–196. <https://doi.org/10.47313/pujangga.v10i2.3917>

Rahmi, A. (2025). Translation strategies for slang in the subtitles of “My Stupid Boss 2.” *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Humaniora*, 3(4), 625–634. <https://doi.org/10.57248/jishum.v3i4.586>

Tasyarasita, A. Z., Duhita, M. E., Yulianti, W., & Yustanto, H. (2023). Ragam bahasa slang oleh remaja Gen Z pada media sosial TikTok (Kajian sosiolinguistik). *Translation and Linguistics (Transling)*, 3(2), 98. <https://doi.org/10.20961/transling.v3i2.74673>

Triadi, R. B., & Pradianti, K. (2025). *Problematika bahasa Indonesia*. Langgam Pustaka.

Wardhani, A. D. (2023). Analisis bahasa slang dalam novel Dikta dan Hukum karya Dhia’an Farah. *Deiksis*, 15(3), 278. <https://doi.org/10.30998/deiksis.v15i3.20979>

Yule, G. (2010). *The study of language* (4th ed.). Cambridge University Press.